

Comprehensive metric-based assessment of fabric phase sorptive extraction's greenness and operational performance in water sample preparation and analysis

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ABSTRACT

Fabric phase sorptive extraction (FPSE) is a sample preparation technique that has gained significant attention due to its operational simplicity, low solvent consumption, and improved sorbent loading relative to traditional extraction techniques. In this study, the greenness and practicality of thirty FPSE-based methods applied to contaminants in environmental water were systematically assessed using four metric tools. As a sample preparation technique, greenness was evaluated according to the Analytical Greenness Metric for Sample Preparation (AGREPrep) and the Sample Preparation Metric of Sustainability (SPMS), yielding score ranges of 0.22 – 0.80 and 6.0 – 8.0, respectively. When considered as complete analytical methodologies, the Analytical GREENness Metric (AGREE) scores ranged between 0.40 and 0.62. Practicality was assessed according to the Blue Applicability Grade Index (BAGI), yielding scores between 55 and 75. Overall, FPSE-based methods were both green and practical. Principal component analysis (PCA) was employed to identify methods achieving satisfactory greenness and practicality. The greenness and practicality of FPSE can be improved by reducing the use of toxic solvents, automation, and using less energy-intensive instrumentation.

1. Introduction

Fabric phase sorptive extraction (FPSE) is an innovative extraction method that combines sol-gel coating technology and surface chemistry of fabrics resulting in an ultra-thin coating with very high sorbent loading [1]. Classical extraction methods such as liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) and solid-phase extraction (SPE) tend to use large volume of toxic and hazardous organic solvents. These also involve tedious and prone to error post-extraction steps. The solid phase microextraction (SPME) has overcome the issues but the SPME fiber has low sorbent loading leading

to poor extraction sensitivity [2]. The FPSE addresses these limitations by combining the exhaustive extraction of SPE and the equilibrium extraction of SPME [2].

FPSE is generally a two-step procedure (extraction and desorption) making it a faster extraction method without using a large volume of hazardous solvents. Moreover, it can preconcentrate target analytes without requiring any additional clean-up. The sorbent made from coating a fabric with sol-gel polymers is very stable making it resistant to harsh chemical environments [3]. Due to these advantages, FPSE has been applied for the analysis of various matrices such as biological [4–6]

Abbreviations: ACN, Acetonitrile; AGREE, Analytical GREENness Metric Approach; AGREPrep, Analytical Greenness Metric for Sample Preparation; BAGI, Blue Applicability Grade Index; CACI, Click Analytical Chemistry Index; CW, carbowax 20M; DAD, diode array detector; ECs, emerging contaminants; EtOAc, ethyl acetate; EtOH, ethanol; FAAS, flame atomic absorption spectrometry; FPSE, fabric phase sorptive extraction; FLD, fluorescence detector; GAC, green analytical chemistry; GAPI, green analytical procedure index; GC, gas chromatography; GEARS, Green Environmental Assessment and Rating of Solvents; GSP, green sample preparation; HPLC, high performance liquid chromatography; IMS, ion mobility spectrometry; LLE, liquid-liquid extraction; MeOH, methanol; MIBK, methyl isobutyl ketone; MOF, molecular organic framework; MS, mass spectrometry; MSDS, material safety data sheet; NEMI, National Environmental Methods Index; NSAIDs, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; PAH, polyaromatic hydrocarbons; PCA, principal component analysis; PCAP, polycaprolactone; PDA, photodiode array; PDMDPS, poly(dimethylphenylsiloxane); PEG, polyethylene glycol; PPCPs, pharmaceuticals and personal care products; PTHF, polytetrahydrofuran; SPE, solid phase extraction; SPME, solid phase microextraction; SPMS, Sample Preparation Metric of Sustainability; UPLC, ultra-performance liquid chromatography; UV, ultraviolet detector; WWTP, wastewater treatment plant.

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and environmental water samples [7]. FPSE has been considered to be an eco-friendly sample preparation technique [8].

The proposal of green chemistry principles by Paul Anastas and John Warner in the 1990's paved way for the introduction of many chemical processes and materials that reduce their negative impact on environmental and human health [9]. The principles applied to analytical chemistry were later proposed and led to the adoption of twelve green analytical chemistry (GAC) principles [10]. The 12 GAC principles have provided guidance in the development of different metrics for evaluating the greenness of analytical chemistry methods.

The first reported tool was the National Environmental Methods Index (NEMI) which assesses analytical methods based on different criteria using a binary response [11]. The Analytical Eco-scale on the other hand is based on assigning penalty points to each greenness category [12]. The Green Analytical Procedure Index (GAPI) and its modified versions—ComplexGAPI and ComplexMoGAPI are green metric tools which provide visual assessments of analytical procedures at each stage [13–15]. Another metric tool called Analytical GREENness Metric Approach (AGREE) also provides a pictogram of the assessment using a unified scale based on the 12 GAC principles [16].

The green chemistry principles were further extended to sample preparation which paved the way to the proposal of ten principles of green sample preparation (GSP) [17]. The Analytical greenness metric for sample preparation (AGREEprep) provides a pictogram assessing the greenness of sample preparation based on ten categories corresponding to the ten principles of GSP [18]. The AGREEprep still accounts for the analytical instrumentation used after the sample preparation. To overcome this, and to focus solely on sample preparation, the Sample Preparation Metric of Sustainability (SPMS) was proposed [19].

The White Analytical Chemistry (WAC) concept was introduced to extend the GAC and the 12 WAC principles were proposed [20]. Whiteness in an analytical method reflects a combination of analytical quality (red), greenness (green), and practicality (blue). As mentioned, different metric tools were developed to assess the greenness of a method. As complementary to these tools, the Blue Applicability Grade Index (BAGI) was developed to assess the practicality of analytical method [21] while the Click Analytical Chemistry Index (CACI) assesses the practicality with emphasis on the costs of analysis [22]. Recently, the Red Analytical Performance Index (RAPI) was proposed to assess the redness of analytical method [23].

The FPSE has been introduced to be a greener extraction method compared to the classical extraction techniques. Owing to its reduced number of steps, this extraction method is regarded as practical. The greenness and practicality of FPSE for the extraction of analytes from biological samples have been published elsewhere [24]. Recent publications on FPSE already included greenness and/or practicality assessments [25,26]. However, the greenness and practicality of FPSE for the extraction of contaminants from environmental water samples published earlier were not yet fully evaluated. To date, only two metric tools are available for assessing the greenness of sample preparation (AGREEprep and SPMS). Complementary to AGREEprep, AGREE can be used for greenness assessment of whole analytical method as both rely on the principles of GAC or GSP. Furthermore, an assessment guideline suggests combining AGREEprep with the AGREE [27]. Both BAGI and CACI assess the practicality of an analytical method. Although CACI provides criterion for the cost of analysis, the data on the costs of reagents are not usually mentioned in published methods. The aim of this article is to provide for the first time a comprehensive integrated evaluation of FPSE-based methods for the analysis of contaminants in environmental water samples in terms of their greenness and practicality using four different metric tools: AGREEprep, SPMS, AGREE and BAGI. Principal component analysis was performed to identify the methods that achieved satisfactory greenness and practicality according to the applied metric tools.

2. Methods

2.1. Selection of FPSE-based methods

The search for the different FPSE-based methods was carried out on the *Scopus* database by typing the keywords “*fabric phase sorptive extraction water*.” Checking the documents and excluding review, non-English language, and non-relevant articles, a total of 30 articles were included in the study, focusing on the use of FPSE to extract contaminants from water [28–57].

2.2. Assessment of greenness and practicality by different metric tools

The FPSE-based methods were evaluated for their greenness both as stand-alone sample preparation techniques, using AGREEprep and SPMS, and as complete analytical methodologies, using the Analytical GREENness Metric (AGREE). On the other hand, the practicality of the whole analytical method involving FPSE was assessed using BAGI. The green metric tools adhere to the principles of green analytical chemistry and green sample preparation. On the other hand, BAGI was based on the principles of white analytical chemistry. The FPSE methods were evaluated based on the available information presented in the published articles. Some assumptions as mentioned in the rest of the article were also made to make the evaluation the same for all the methods.

2.3. AGREEprep

In this metric tool, the greenness of sample preparation is assessed based on ten criteria (Table 1) corresponding to the ten principles of green sample preparation [17]. The assessment of FPSE methods were done using the freely available web-based application (<https://agreeprep.anvil.app>) that automatically generates a pictogram (Fig. 1). The pictogram is circular and consists of ten trapezoidal segments, with each segment corresponding to a specific criterion and colored based on its score (ranging from red to green). The length of the trapezoid correlates to the assigned weight. Default weights were used during the assessment. The overall greenness score (with 1.0 being the highest) is shown at the center of the pictogram [18,58].

To assess the impact of reusability of FPSE membranes on the greenness of the extraction procedure, two scenarios were assessed. Scenario 1 refers to the actual information provided in the published methods allowing the reusability of the FPSE membrane, considering the use of organic solvents for the cleaning and conditioning of the membrane prior to reuse. On the other hand, Scenario 2 assumes that a new pre-conditioned FPSE membrane was used, and that cleaning was done using only deionized water and the membrane was never reused. If the methods include salt and/or pH adjustments, the use of 0.1 g of reagents was assumed. The weight of FPSE membrane was assumed to be less than 0.1 g for all the methods.

2.4. SPMS

SPMS is another metric tool used to assess the greenness of FPSE as sample preparation. The assessment is based on ten criteria (Table 1), each of which was found to impact greenness. The FPSE methods were assessed using an Excel file provided by the creators of the metric tool. In the Excel sheet, a clock-type pictogram is automatically generated (Fig. 1) where each rounded square corresponds to a criterion and is colored from red to green indicating the greenness characteristics. Criterion 10, which refers to reusability, is indicated by a star-shaped mark. The overall score (with 10 being the highest) is shown at the center of the pictogram [19].

2.5. AGREE

The overall greenness of FPSE-based methods was assessed using this

Table 1

Criteria for the assessment of greenness and practicality according to the metric tools used (corresponding scores in parenthesis).

Criterion	AGREEprep	SPMS	AGREE	BAGI
1	Sample preparation mode <i>In-line/In situ</i> (1) <i>On-line/In situ</i> (0.66) <i>On site</i> (0.33) <i>Ex-situ</i> (0)	Sample amount $x \leq 10$ (5) $10 < x \leq 50$ (3) $50 < x \leq 100$ (2) $x > 100$ (1)	Sample preparation mode remote sensing w/o sample damage (1); remote sensing w/ little damage (0.95); noninvasive (0.90); in-field and direct (0.85); in-field and on-line (0.78); on-line (0.70); at-line (0.60); off-line (0.48); external treatment and batch with reduced steps (0.30); external treatment and batch with large number of steps (0)	Type of analysis Quantitative and cofirmatory (10) Quantitative (7.5) Screening (5) Qualitative (2.5)
2	Amount of hazardous solvents/ reagents (Score = $-0.145 \times \ln(\text{amount}) + 0.3333$)	Amount of extractant $x \leq 0.1$ (20) $0.1 < x \leq 0.5$ (12) $0.5 < x \leq 1$ (6) $x > 1$ (2)	Amount of sample Ultramicro/micro/semimicro (1) Macro (score = $-0.142 \times \ln(\text{amount}) + 0.65$)	Number of analytes Multi-element, >15 (10) Multi-element, 6-15 same class or 2-15 different classes (7.5) Multi-element, 2-5 same class (5) Sinfle element (2.5)
3	Type of materials 100% of materials are sustainable (1) >75% of materials are sustainable (0.75) 50-75% of materials are sustainable (0.5) Materials not sustainable but used several times (0.5) 25-50% of materials are sustainable (0.25) <25% of materials are sustainable (0)	Nature of extractant Natural (10) Alternative degradable (6) Alternative persistent (3) Converntional persistent (1)	Location of analytical device <i>In-line</i> (1) <i>On-line</i> (0.66) <i>At-line</i> (0.33) <i>Off-line</i> (0)	Analytical technique Simple in operation (10) Available in most labs (7.5) Sophisticated instruments (5) Not commonly available (2.5)
4	Amount of waste (Score = $-0.161 \times \ln(\text{amount}) + 0.6295$)	Number of steps $x \leq 2$ (10) $2 < x \leq 4$ (6) $4 < x \leq 6$ (3) $x > 6$ (1)	Number of steps ≤ 3 steps (1) 4 steps (0.8) 5 steps (0.6) 6 steps (0.4)	Number of samples >95 (10) 13-95 (7.5) 2-12 (5) 1 (2.5)
5	Amount of sample (Score = $-0.145 \times \ln(\text{amount}) + 0.6667$)	Extraction time $x \leq 5$ (10) $5 < x \leq 15$ (6) $15 < x \leq 60$ (3) $x > 60$ (1)	Automation and miniaturization Automatic, miniaturized (1) Semi-automatic, miniturized (0.75) Manual, minitaurized (0.5) Automatic, not miniaturized (0.5) Semi-automatic, not miniaturized (0.25) Manual, not miniaturized (0)	Sample preparation technique Not required or on-site (10) Simple low-cost (7.5) Miniaturized extraction (5) Multi-step (2.5)
6	Sample throughput (Score = $0.2354 \times \ln(\text{samples per hour})$)	Additional steps No additional steps (10) Dilution (5) Evaporation (3) Derivatization (3)	Derivatization Scores depend on derivatization reagent	Sample throughput >10 (10) 5-10 (7.5) 2-4 (5) ≤ 1 (2.5)
7	Number of steps and automation ≤ 2 steps (1) 3 steps (0.75) 4 steps (0.5) 5 steps (0.25) ≥ 6 steps (0) Fully-automates (1) Semi-automated (0.5) Manual (0.25)	Sample throughput Multiple samples (mark) Single sample (no mark)	Amount of waste (score = $-0.134 \times \ln(\text{amount}) + 0.6946$)	Type of reagents/ materials Common, commercially available (10) Commercially available but not common (7.5) Need to be synthesized in simple way (5) Need to be synthesized with advanced equipment (2)
8	Energy consumption <10 Wh per sample (1) 10-500 Wh per sample (score = $-0.256 \times \ln(\text{Wh/sample}) + 1.5886$) >500 Wh per sample (0)	Energy consumption manual shake (3), vortex (3), ultrasound (3), pump (2), stirrer (1), shaker (1), no centrifugation (2), centrifugation (1), room temperature (5), microwave (3), heater (1), freezer (1)	Analytical throughput (score = $0.2429 \times \ln(\text{number of analytes determine in } 1 \text{ h}) - 0.0517$)	Preconcentration No preconcentration required (10) One-step preconcentration (7.5) Preconcentration required with many steps (2.5)
9	Analytical technique Simple (1) Spectroscopic (0.75) GC/LC with non MS detection (0.5) GC/LC with MS (0.25) Advanced MS (0)	Total waste $x \leq 10$ (10) $10 < x \leq 50$ (6) $50 < x \leq 100$ (3) $x > 100$ (1)	Energy consumption <0.1 KWh per sample (1) 0.1–1.5 KWh per sample (0.5) >1.5 KWh per sample (0)	Automation Fully automated (10) Semi-automated with common devices (7.5) Semi-automated with non-common devices (5) Manual treatment and analysis (2.5)
10	Number of hazards No hazards (1) 1 hazard (0.75) 2 hazards (0.5)	Reusability Yes (mark) No (no mark)	Source of reagents All are bio-based (1) Some are bio-based (0.5) No reagents are bio-based (0)	Amount of sample $\leq 100 \mu\text{L}$ (or mg) for bioanalytical, $\leq 10 \text{ mL}$ (or g) for food/environmental/other (10) $101\text{--}500 \mu\text{L}$ (or mg) for

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Table 1 (continued)

Criterion	AGREEprep	SPMS	AGREE	BAGI
	3 hazards (0.25) ≥ 4 hazards (0)			bioanalytical, 10.1–50 mL (or g) for food/environmental/other (7.5) 501–1000 µL (or mg) for bioanalytical, 51–100 mL (or g) for food/environmental/other (5) >1000 µL (or mg) for bioanalytical, >100 mL (or g) for food/environmental/other (7.5)
11			Amount of toxic solvents/ reagents (score = $-0.156 \times \ln(\text{amount}) + 0.5898$)	
12			Number of hazards No threats (0); 1 threat (0.8); 2 threats (0.6); 3 threats (0.4); 4 threats (0.2)	

Fig. 1. Pictogram results annotated by criterion numbers for the different metric tools used: a) AGREEprep; b) SPMS; c) AGREE; and d) BAGI.

metric tool. It is based on the assessment of 12 criteria (Table 1) corresponding to the principles of green analytical chemistry. The assessment was done using the freely available software (<https://mostwiedzy.pl/AGREE>). It automatically generates a circular pictogram (Fig. 1) with parts corresponding to each criterion. Default weights for each criterion were used during the assessment. Each part of the pictogram is colored according to its green character (red to green). The overall score (with 1.0 being the highest) can be seen at the center of the pictogram [16].

2.6. BAGI

The practicality of FPSE-based methods was evaluated using this complementary tool. The practicality was assessed based on ten categories (Table 1). Assessments were performed using a freely available web-based application (<https://bagi-index.anvil.app>), which automatically generates an asteroid pictogram (Fig. 1). The segments of the pictogram correspond to each category and are colored from white, light blue, and dark blue corresponding from no to high practicality. The overall score (with 100 being the highest) is shown at the middle part of the pictogram [21].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Greenness of FPSE as sample preparation technique

3.1.1. Greenness according to AGREEprep

The greenness of FPSE as sample preparation technique was first assessed using AGREEprep and the resulting scores and pictograms are shown in Table 2 (Scenario 1). All the FPSE methods were performed *ex-situ* and had zero score on criterion 1 indicated by a red color on the first trapezoidal part of the pictograms. Water samples were collected and

transported to the laboratory before doing the extraction procedures.

In criterion 2, the methods had different scores based on the volume of toxic solvents used. Most methods used methanol (MeOH) either for cleaning and washing of the FPSE membranes or as elution solvent. MeOH was considered hazardous because of its acute toxicity (toxic if inhaled, swallowed, or in contact with skin). Toxic dichloromethane was also used for the conditioning of FPSE membrane for the extraction of phthalates [56]. Thus, these methods received orange to red colors on the second trapezoidal part of the pictograms. Ethyl acetate was used for the elution of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) [32] while methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) was used for the analysis of metals [34]. On the other hand, acetonitrile (ACN) was used as elution solvent for brominated flame retardants [37], multiclass emerging contaminants (ECs) [43], polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) [44], and fluoroquinolones [50]. Since these solvents were not considered hazardous, the corresponding FPSE-based methods received green color on the pictograms' second trapezoid.

Most methods used sustainable and renewable materials and thus displayed green colors for criterion 3. FPSE membranes can be prepared from natural fabrics such as cellulose, and the elution solvent like methanol can be produced from natural sources. FPSE membranes are also reusable, further enhancing their sustainability. PEG-coated polyester membranes for the extraction of NSAIDs [32] and carbowax-coated cellulose fabrics for the extraction of multiclass ECs [43] can be used up to 30 times. For the extraction of pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs) [38] and parabens [42], the FPSE membranes can be reused for 20 times. On the other hand, for the on-line FPSE extraction of lead and cadmium, the FPSE disk can be used for up to 500 times [34]. The extraction efficiency of the reusable FPSE membrane for the extraction of pesticides did not decrease by more than 10% [54].

The amount of waste produced during the FPSE process concerns criterion 4. Most methods had yellow to orange color on fourth trapezoidal part of the pictogram which generated between 2 to 20 mL of waste coming from the use of solvents for the cleaning, conditioning, and washing of FPSE membranes, as well as the elution solvent. The amount of waste also includes the reagents used for pH and ionic strength adjustments, as well as the weight of the membranes. Methods for the extraction of PPCPs [38], parabens [42], and UV filters [49] generated around 30 to 50 mL of waste due to large volumes of solvents used for FPSE membrane conditioning and washing, and for sample adjustments. These methods received a red color for criterion 4 on the pictogram. Greenish color was obtained for the extraction of estrogens using polytetrahydrofuran (PTHF)-coated cellulose fabric since it only generated less than 2 mL of waste [29]. A method for the extraction of PAHs using polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)-coated microfiber glass generated the least amount of waste (solvent less) since the desorption was done thermally [44], hence had the greenest color for criterion 4.

Criterion 5 refers to the amount of sample. Different volumes of water samples were used for the extraction of the contaminants

Table 2
Results of the greenness and practicality assessments of FPSE- based methods.

Method	Contaminants (Number of Analytes)	Water Sample Matrix (volume, mL)	FPSE Sorbent / desorption solvent (volume, mL)	Extraction Time (min) / Desorption Time (min)	Analytical Technique (run time, min)	AGREEprep Scenario 1	AGREEprep Scenario 2	SPMS	AGREE	BAGI	Ref.
1	estrogens (3)	ground water drinking water river water WWTP effluent (10)	PTHF-coated cellulose / MeOH (0.5)	20 / 8	HPLC-FLD (6)						[28]
2	alkyl phenols (4)	ground water river water WWTP effluent (10)	PTHF-coated cellulose / MeOH (0.5)	20 / 6	HPLC-UV (6)						[29]
3	pharmaceuticals and personal care products (14)	river water WWTP effluent WWTP influent (10)	PEG-coated cellulose / MeOH (1)	240 / 5	LC-MS/MS (20)						[30]
4	UV stabilizers (7)	effluent (10)	PDMDPS-coated polyester / MeOH (0.5)	60 / 5	UPLC-MS/MS (2)						[31]
5	non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (4)	river water influent effluent (30)	PEG-coated polyester / EtOAc (1)	120 / 15	GC-MS (38.2)						[32]
6 (stir-FPSE)	triazine herbicides (7)	stream river water (100)	PEG-coated cellulose / MeOH (1)	60 / 5	LC-MS/MS (12)						[33]
7 (disk-FPSE)	metal (1)	river water coastal water seawater ditch (6)	PDMDPS-coated polyester / MIBK (2)	1.5 / 0.47	FAAS						[34]
8	UV stabilizers (7)	seawater (25)	PDMDPS-coated cellulose / MeOH (1)	150 / 10	UPLC-MS/MS (2)						[35]
9	hormones (10)	WWTP effluent hospital influent (10)	PTHF-coated cellulose / MeOH (0.75)	20 / 3	UPLC-MS/MS (6.5)						[36]
10a (stir-bar FPSE)	brominated flame retardants (3)	wastewater (10)	PTHF-coated cellulose / ACN (0.3)	10 / 10	HPLC-DAD (30)						[37]
10b (magnetic-FPSE)	brominated flame retardants (3)	wastewater (10)	PTHF-coated cellulose / ACN (0.3)	15 / 15	HPLC-DAD (30)						[37]
10c	brominated flame retardants (3)	wastewater (10)	PTHF-coated cellulose / ACN (0.3)	20 / 10	HPLC-DAD (30)						[37]

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Table 2 (continued)

11 (dynamic FPSE)	Pharmaceuticals and personal care products (14)	river water WWTP influent WWTP effluent (50)	CW-coated cellulose / EtOAc (10)	10 / 10	LC-MS/MS (42)						[38]
12	polyaromatic hydrocarbons (4)	river water rain water drinking water (15)	C18-coated cellulose / ACN (0.3)	30 / 5	HPLC-FLD (10)						[39]
13	cytostatic drugs (7)	wastewater effluent (10)	CW-coated cellulose / MeOH (1)	60 / 5	UPLC- MS/MS (6)						[40]
14	metal (1)	surface water industrial wastewater (10)	C18-coated cellulose / ACN (0.5)	20 / 15	HPLC-UV (8)						[41]
15	parabens (3)	river water wastewater (10)	CW-coated cellulose / MeOH (0.7)	40 / 1.5	HPLC-PDA (18)						[42]
16	multiclass compounds of emerging concern (8)	tap water municipal water ground water sewage water (10)	CW-coated cellulose / acetone (0.4)	25 / 10	GC-MS (20.33)						[43]
17	polyaromatic hydrocarbons (3)	river water reclaimed water (5)	PDMS-coated microfiber glass / thermal	20	IMS						[44]
18	fungicides (17)	tap water spring water fountain water rain water run off water river water (20)	CW-coated cellulose / EtOAc (0.5)	20 / 30	GC-MS/MS (22.5)						[45]
19	antidepressants (5)	WWTP influent WWTP effluent hospital influent hospital effluent lake water (1)	PEG-coated microfiber glass / MeOH (1)	30 / 10	HPLC-DAD (15)						[46]
20	pharmaceuticals and acesulfame (21)	city wastewater hospital wastewater (10)	PEG-coated microfiber glass / MeOH (2)	35 / 20	UPLC- Orbitrap (10)						[47]
21	pesticide residues (2)	river water lake water pond water (10)	PCAP-PDMS- PCAP-coated cellulose / MeOH (0.2)	30 / 0.5	HPLC-PDA (25)						[48]

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Table 2 (continued)

22	UV filters (6)	river water lake water sea water (150)	MOF-coated cotton / MeOH (2.25)	60 / 15	HPLC-UV (20)						[49]
23 (stir bar-FPSE)	fluoroquinolones (4)	wastewater reservoir water river water lake water (10)	PEG-coated cellulose / ACN:acetic acid (0.3)	10 / 15	HPLC-UV (15)						[50]
24 (magnet-integrated FPSE)	benzoyl urea insecticides (5)	tap water mineral water lake water river water (100)	CW-coated cellulose / MeOH (1.1)	40 / 2	HPLC-DAD (10)						[51]
25	anthracyclines (3)	sewage water (20)	PCAP-PDMS-PCAP-coated cellulose / MeOH (1.4)	15 / 8	UPLC-FLD (5)						[52]
26	synthetic musks (12)	wastewater bathwater seawater spring water laundry water swimming pool water washing machine water mop water (100)	PDMS-coated cellulose / EtOH (0.5)	15 / 5	GC-MS/MS (13.3)						[53]
27 (magnet-integrated FPSE)	multiclass pesticides (41)	river water pond water lake water (100)	PTHF/CW-coated polyester / acetone (0.25)	50 / 2	GC-MS (30)						[54]
28	antidiabetics (10)	WWTP influent WWTP effluent hospital influent hospital effluent lake water river water (1)	PEG-coated microfiber glass / ACN (0.1)	45 / 10	HPLC-DAD (10)						[55]
29	phthalates (10)	bottled water tap water pond water (40)	CW-coated cellulose / ACN (0.5)	30 / 10	HPLC-UV (22)						[56]
30	endocrine disrupting compounds (10)	tap water pond water (30)	CW-coated cellulose / ACN (0.25)	45 / 10	HPLC-UV (19)						[57]

ACN: acetonitrile; CW: carbowax 20M; EtOAc: ethyl acetate; EtOH: ethanol; FAAS: flame atomic absorption spectrometry; FLD: fluorescence detector; GC: gas chromatography; HPLC: high performance liquid chromatography; IMS: ion mobility spectrometry; MeOH: methanol; MIBK: methyl isobutyl ketone; MOF: molecular organic framework; MS: mass spectrometry; PCAP: polycaprolactone; PDMDPS: poly(dimethylphenylsiloxane); PEG: polyethylene glycol; PTHF: polytetrahydrofuran; UPLC: ultra-performance liquid chromatography; UV: ultraviolet detector; WWTP: wastewater treatment plant.

(Table 2). In most cases, 10 mL sample volume was used for the FPSE procedure which got an orange color on the fifth trapezoidal part of the pictogram. Some FPSE methods had red color due to the use of large volumes for the extraction– 50 mL, 100 mL, and 150 mL for the extraction of 14 PPCPs [38], seven triazine herbicides [33], and six UV filters [49], respectively. On the other hand, FPSE methods for the extraction of five antidepressants [46] and ten antidiabetic drugs [55] which only used 1 mL sample volume had green color on the fifth

trapezoidal part of their pictograms.

The sample throughput of FPSE methods varies depending on the optimized extraction/desorption time, and they mostly displayed yellow to green colors for criterion 6 on their pictograms (Table 2). In classical FPSE, magnetic stirrer is used for the agitation of the sample which was assumed to accommodate up to ten samples at a time. Due to the use of a large volume of sample, the extraction of six UV filters was estimated to accommodate about four samples at a time on a magnetic stirring plate,

and with an extraction/desorption time of about 75 min, the sample throughput was only 1.9 samples per hour leading to a red-orange color on the sixth trapezoidal part of its pictogram [49]. About 245 minutes was required for the extraction of 14 PPCPs resulted in an overall calculated sample throughput of 2.2 samples per hour which displayed a red- orange color on its pictogram [30]. The greenest methods for criterion 6 were the extraction of PAHs with a sample throughput of about 30 samples per hour which only involved thermal desorption [44] and the online extraction of heavy metals with a calculated sample throughput of 30.6 samples per hour [34].

FPSE primarily involves two main steps: extraction and desorption. For complex sample matrices, an additional sample clean-up step may be required. Derivatization may also be required as in the case of the extraction of NSAIDs [32], while reconstitution may be necessary for the extraction of triazine herbicides [33], multiclass pharmaceuticals [47], benzoyl urea insecticides [51], and anthracyclines [52]. Automation is a big factor in the greenness of the method. However, in most cases, FPSE is done manually. Thus, all the FPSE methods assessed displayed yellow to red- orange colors for criterion 7 on the pictograms (Table 2). The semi-automated system for the online extraction of heavy metals had the highest score on this criterion [34].

The total energy consumption of the FPSE procedures was estimated based on the assumptions on the energy consumption of common laboratory equipment given by Peris-Pastor and co-authors [59]. The energy consumption of the FPSE methods ranged from 0.67 Wh/sample for the extraction of EDCs [36] and PAHs [44], up to 20.2 Wh/sample for the extraction of PPCPs [30] which mostly only used magnetic stirrer (20 W) that can accommodate up to ten samples at a time. All of the FPSE methods (Table 2) received green color for criterion 8 on their pictograms, except for method 11 that was developed for the extraction of PPCPs and displayed a yellow color due to energy consumption of 63 Wh/sample [38]. The method was assumed to use a 350 W vacuum for the extraction which was performed one sample at a time for 10 minutes, and ultrasonic bath (330 W) that could accommodate up to 12 samples simultaneously.

Criterion 9 refers to the analytical instrumentation employed after the FPSE procedure. For the analysis of contaminants, liquid chromatography was the most used technique (Table 2). Methods which used high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with fluorescence (FLD), UV-Visible (UV) or diode array (DA) detector [28,29,37,39,41,42,46,48–52,55–57] had yellow color on the ninth part of their pictograms due to the consumption of mobile phases. Yellow can also be seen on the pictogram of the method which used flame atomic absorption spectroscopy (FAAS) for the analysis of lead and cadmium [34]. Gas chromatography- mass spectrometry (GCMS)- based methods for the analysis of NSAIDs [32], multiclass emerging contaminants [43], and multiclass pesticides [54] displayed orange color on their pictograms due to high energy consumption. On the other hand, higher energy is required for the analysis using advanced mass spectrometry (MS) techniques [30,31,33,35,36,38,45,47,52,53] leading to a red color on the ninth part of their pictograms. The greenest method was the use of bench top ion mobility spectrometry for the onsite analysis of PAHs [44].

Criterion 10 ensures that the procedures are safe for the operator. The FPSE methods were assessed by counting the number of threats the chemicals used has based on their material safety data sheets (MSDS). Since most of the FPSE methods assessed used MeOH (four hazards- flammable, toxic, and health) and ACN (two hazards- flammable and irritant), on the average, 3 to 4 hazards can be observed in every FPSE methods resulting to an orange to red color on their pictograms (Table 2). Only two hazards were noted for the extraction of heavy metals [34] and brominated flame retardants [37] which used chemicals that are only flammable and irritant. In the extraction of PAHs, the analytes were desorbed thermally making it solvent-less, thus there was no observed hazard resulting to a green color on its pictogram for criterion 10 [44].

The average overall AGREEprep score of the FPSE-based methods for

the extraction of contaminants in water is 0.45 out of the maximum score of 1. The lowest obtained AGREEprep score was 0.22 for the extraction of 14 PPCPs which used large amount of toxic solvent for the FPSE membrane conditioning and cleaning; considered large volume of sample; generated large amount of waste; had high energy consumption; and used advanced MS technique for the analysis [38]. On the other hand, maximum AGREEprep score of 0.8 was obtained for the extraction of three PAHs since it did not involve toxic solvents; used lower sample volume; generated lowest amount of waste; had high sample throughput; with less energy consumption; and used less sophisticated analytical technique [44].

As mentioned, the FPSE membranes can be reused many times without losing their extraction efficiency. However, reusing the FPSE membranes involves the use of large volumes of toxic solvents for the cleaning, washing, and conditioning, making the FPSE methods less green. FPSE membranes can be prepared in-house and do not require special equipment making them inexpensive. Thus, they can be used as single-use membranes to minimize solvent consumption during cleaning/washing [29]. Using single-use FPSE membrane could potentially increase the greenness of the method.

The FPSE-based methods were re-assessed assuming that the FPSE membranes were used only once, did not require toxic solvents for cleaning and washing, and used only water for conditioning. Doing so, the pictograms changed colors for criteria 2, 3, and 4 which correspond to the volume of toxic solvents, the sustainability of materials, and the amount of generated waste. The result of the re-assessment is shown on Table 2 (AGREEprep Scenario 2). The average overall AGREEprep score improved from 0.45 to 0.53, with an average increase of 0.08. Those methods which did not use MeOH, minimal change was observed. There was no change in the AGREEprep score of the FPSE method for the extraction of heavy metals [34] since it did not use toxic solvents. Since the FPSE membranes were not reused, the degree of renewability of materials and reagents used have decreased resulting in the slight decrease in the AGREEprep total scores of the methods for extraction of triazine herbicides (0.4 to 0.39) [33], PAHs (0.8 to 0.78) [44], and fluoroquinolones (0.57 to 0.56) [50]. The highest AGREEprep score of 0.78 remained for the extraction of PAHs [44]. On the other hand, the lowest score in Scenario 1 which is the extraction of PPCPs, improved by 100% from 0.22 to 0.44 total AGREEprep score [38].

The AGREEprep assessments have shown that eliminating the use of toxic solvents for FPSE membrane conditioning, cleaning, and washing could improve the greenness of the method. To further assess the greenness of the FPSE as sample preparation technique, the FPSE methods were evaluated according to the SPMS metric tool.

3.1.2. Greenness according to SPMS

One of the limitations of AGREEprep tool is that it still considers the final analytical technique in the evaluation of the greenness of sample preparation method which greatly affects the overall score when advanced instrumentation technique is used. SPMS addresses this limitation by solely evaluating the sample preparation technique [19]. The SPMS criteria are divided into four based on the information related to the sample (criterion 1), extractant (criteria 2 and 3), procedure (criteria 4, 5, and 6), and energy consumption and waste (criteria 8 and 9). Criteria 7 and 10 refer to the sample throughput and reusability which are indicated by marks on the pictogram. Scores were given to the FPSE methods according to the scoring matrix of the metric tool [19]. Resulting pictograms of the evaluation are presented in Table 2. The colors of each section of the pictograms varied according to the increasing level of greenness (red, orange, yellow, green).

For criterion 1, the extraction procedure using a sample volume greater than 100 mL received a red color on first rounded square of the pictogram, as in the extraction of UV filters requiring 150 mL of water sample [49]. The extractions of triazine herbicides [33], PPCPs [38], benzoyl urea insecticides [51], and multiclass pesticides [54] required sample volumes of up to 100 mL resulting to an orange color on their

pictograms. The extractions of contaminants using sample volume of more than 10 mL up to 50 mL displayed a yellow color (Table 2). The greenest methods according to SPMS criterion 1 are those that used a sample volume of 10 mL or less.

Criterion 2 of the SPMS tool refers to the amount of the extractant–the FPSE membranes. In the evaluation, it was assumed that all the FPSE membranes had a weight of less than 0.1 g, thus all the methods received green color on the second rounded square of their pictograms. On the other hand, criterion 3 assesses the nature of the extractants whether they are conventional and persistent, alternative and persistent, alternative and degradable, or natural which correspond to red, orange, yellow or green color. Depending on where the FPSE membrane is made from, the degree of greenness on this criterion varies. Microfiber glass and polyester-based FPSE membranes are not biodegradable, thus can be categorized as alternative and persistent. Hence, the FPSE methods [31,32,34,44,46,47,54,55] using these membranes displayed orange color on criterion 3 for their pictograms. The rest of the methods used cellulose which is a natural fiber but since it is coated with synthetic polymers, it can be categorized as alternative and degradable. These methods received yellow color on the pictograms.

Criterion 4 of SPMS refers to the number of steps. In this metric tool, procedural steps relate to the parts of the procedure when the extractant is in contact with the sample; wherein the last step is the elution of the target analytes from the extractant [19]. Given this context, FPSE is a two-step procedure comprising of only the extraction and the elution steps. Thus, all the FPSE methods evaluated received a green color for criterion 4 of their pictograms. Criterion 5 entails the length of the extraction procedures. According to this tool, sample preparation method with extraction time (extraction/elution) of more than 60 minutes corresponds to a red color on the criterion 5 of the pictogram. The extractions of 14 PPCPs [30], seven UV stabilizers [31], four NSAIDs [32], seven triazine herbicides [33], six UV stabilizers [35], seven cytostatic drugs [40], and six UV filters [49] required 245 min, 65 min, 135 min, 65 min, 160 min, 65 min, and 120 min, respectively, thus received red colors on the fifth rounded square of their pictograms. The majority of the FPSE methods evaluated had extraction times between 15 and 60 minutes and therefore displayed an orange color on the pictograms (Table 2). None of the thirty FPSE methods evaluated had an extraction time between 5 and 15 min, which could have resulted in a yellow color on the pictogram. The online extraction of heavy metals can be completed within 2 min [34], making it the greenest method evaluated for criterion 5. Additional steps after extraction relate to criterion 6, where no additional steps, dilution, evaporation, and derivatization correspond to green, orange, red, and red colors, respectively, on the sixth rounded square of the pictogram. Most of the FPSE methods evaluated did not require additional steps or only involved centrifugation of the eluent, and hence, received a green color for criterion 6 on the pictograms (Table 2). The extractions of 14 PPCPs [30], four NSAIDs [32], seven triazine herbicides [33], 14 PPCPs [38], five antidepressants [46], 20 pharmaceuticals [47], five benzoyl urea insecticides [51], and three anthracycline [52] required evaporation/reconstitution or derivatization, thus displayed red color for criterion 6 on their pictograms. In SPMS tool, the sample throughput of the extraction method is indicated by a frame for criteria 4, 5, and 6 on the pictogram. A frame can be seen on the pictogram for the FPSE methods that can extract multiple samples at a time (Table 2). In different FPSE approaches such as disk [34], stir-bar [37,50], and dynamic [38] FPSE, the extraction can be performed only one sample at a time. Therefore, these methods did not have a frame for criteria 4, 5, and 6 on their pictograms.

The energy consumption of sample preparation method is assessed in SPMS metric tool based on the type of dispersion (manual shaking, vortex, ultrasound, pump, stirrer, shaker), separation (without or with centrifugation), and temperature (room temperature, microwave, heater, cooler/freezer). The majority of the FPSE methods evaluated used a stirring plate, without centrifugation, and assumed done under room temperature, received yellow color for criterion 8 on their

pictograms (Table 2). The extractions of heavy metals [34] and 14 PPCPs [38] required the use of pumps, while the extraction of 12 synthetic musks [53] and ten antidiabetic drugs [55] used ultrasound bath and vortex mixer, respectively. These methods displayed green color for criterion 8 on their pictograms. The extraction of three PAHs required thermal desorption at 50 °C [44], therefore received red color for criterion 8.

For criterion 9, the total waste including the amount of sample is evaluated. In SPMS tool, extraction procedures with greater than 100 mL (or g) of waste, from 51 to 100 mL (or g), from 11 to 50 mL (or g), and 10 mL (or g) or less will have red, orange, yellow, and green colors on the criterion 9 of the pictograms. The extractions of seven triazine herbicides [33], six UV filters [49], five benzoyl urea insecticides, and 41 multiclass pesticides [54] generated about 103 mL, 203 mL, 110 mL, and 111 mL of waste, including the sample, and therefore had red colors on the ninth rounded square of their pictograms. Orange colors appear for criterion 9 on the pictograms for the extraction of 14 PPCPs [38] and three parabens [42] which generated approximately 91 mL and 55 mL of waste, respectively. Most of the FPSE methods evaluated received a yellow color for criterion 9 on their pictograms (Table 2) while the extraction of three PAHs [44], five antidepressants [46], and ten antidiabetic drugs [55] were the greenest for this criterion.

Criterion 10 refers to the reusability of the extractant used and marked by a star-like shape on the pictogram. As mentioned before, FPSE membranes are reusable and therefore all of the FPSE methods evaluated had this mark (Table 2).

For each criterion of the SPMS metric tool, scores were given. The average total SPMS score of the FPSE methods evaluated was 7.25, which means that the FPSE methods evaluated have a satisfactory green characteristic according to this metric tool. The lowest total SPMS score of 6.0 was obtained for the extractions of four NSAIDs [32] and seven triazine herbicides [33] due to low scores obtained related to the extraction time and additional steps. The highest score of 8.00 was obtained by the FPSE method for the extraction of heavy metals [34]. The method received high scores (green colors) for most of the criteria except for the criteria related to the nature of extractant and the amount of waste.

Unlike in AGREEprep, re-assessment was not performed (changing the amount of solvents/waste) since the evaluation criteria for the amount of waste in SPMS is categorical. Changes in the amount of solvents/waste will not differ significantly.

3.1.3. Comparison between AGREEprep and SPMS metric tools

To compare the two metric tools, the scores were normalized to 100% by multiplying the AGREEprep scores by 100 and the SPMS scores by 10. The normalized scores are shown in Fig. 2a. In general, SPMS scores are higher than the AGREEprep scores (Fig. 3). This difference is due to the relative weights of the criteria assessed in the overall score. With the default weights, the amount of toxic solvent(s) has the highest impact on the overall AGREEprep score, while the extractant information has the greatest impact on the SPMS score. In AGREEprep, methanol is considered as hazardous solvent due to its toxicity according to its MSDS, although it is more environmentally friendly compared with other solvents like acetonitrile [51,60]. According to Green Environmental Assessment and Rating for Solvents (GEARS), methanol had a score of 77 while acetonitrile had a score of 73 [61]. AGREEprep gives low importance to the sample preparation mode while the sample amount is given low importance for the SPMS. It is evident that the greenest FPSE method for the AGREEprep metric was the extraction of PAHs [44] because it did not involve solvents for the desorption of the analytes. On the other hand, the SPMS gave the highest rating for the on-line extraction of heavy metals [34] due to low consumption of solvent and less energy requirements.

In AGREEprep, the sample is not considered waste if it is not contaminated with other chemicals [58]. On the other hand, the sample is considered waste in the SPMS metric, however, the scoring for this

Fig. 2. Greenness scores of the FPSE as a sample preparation technique (a) and greenness and practicality of FPSE-based methods (b).

criterion is not restrictive compared with the AGREEprep (Fig. 3). For instance, a 10 mL of waste is considered green according to SPMS. However, in AGREEprep, a 10 mL of waste would result in an orange color. Changes in the amount of waste will give a new score for AGREEprep (change in color). On the other hand, small changes in the amount of waste will not change the SPMS score.

The sample throughput of the extraction method affects the total score of the AGREEprep while it is only indicated by a mark in the SPMS pictogram. The AGREEprep scores for the extraction of three brominated flame retardants changed when done in different FPSE approaches [37]. The stir-bar FPSE had a lower score of 0.56 compared with the magnetic FPSE and classical FPSE which both had 0.61 total score (Table 2). This is because, in stir-bar FPSE, analyte extraction is performed on a single sample at a time, whereas other approaches allow the simultaneous extraction of multiple samples. On the other hand, the SPMS scores for the said extraction in different approaches did not change.

Despite the differences between the metrics, a correlation plot based on their normalized scores was generated to assess whether a high AGREEprep score corresponds to a high SPMS score (Fig. 4a). Method 7 exhibited the highest SPMS score and was among the highest in AGREEprep. In contrast, Methods 22 and 11 exhibited the lowest AGREEprep scores and also ranked low according to SPMS. This indicates a moderate correlation between AGREEprep and SPMS, as confirmed by Spearman's correlation coefficient ($\rho = 0.59$, p -value = 0.00042). Nevertheless, the data suggest that a high AGREEprep score

does not always guarantee a high SPMS score.

In general, the focus of the AGREEprep metric in assessing the greenness of a method is on the solvent usage, waste generation, energy consumption and safety. On the other hand, the SPMS prioritizes the miniaturization, procedural efficiency and energy consumption to lessen the method's environmental impact [62].

3.2. Greenness of FPSE-based methods as whole analytical methods according to AGREE

Using AGREE metric tool, the overall greenness of FPSE-based methods for the analysis of contaminants in environmental water was assessed. The greenness of the methods was evaluated according to 12 criteria (Table 2) corresponding to the 12 principles of green analytical chemistry.

In criterion 1, highest greenness is assigned to a method when direct analytical technique is applied and avoids sample treatment. Although FPSE can be applied on-site, all the FPSE-based methods evaluated required external sample treatment and batch analysis with reduced number of steps, thus all of them had orange color on the pictograms for criterion 1.

The sample amount relates to criterion 2. Red colors for criterion 2 on the pictograms can be seen for methods with sample volumes equal to or greater than 30 mL, including the analyses of four NSAIDs [32], seven triazine herbicides [33], 14 PPCPs [38], six UV filters [49], five benzoyl

Fig. 3. Box plot of the scores according to metric tools used.

Fig. 4. Scatter plot showing correlation between AGREEprep and SPMS (a) and between AGREE and BAGI (b).

urea insecticides, and 41 multiclass pesticides [54]. On the other hand, the analyses of seven UV stabilizers [35], 17 fungicides [45], and three anthracyclines [52] required 20 to 25 mL of water sample which received red-orange color on the criterion 2 of their pictograms. In most cases, the FPSE-based methods evaluated used 10 mL of sample and displayed orange color on their pictograms for the said criterion. While a yellow color can be seen for the analysis of heavy metals [34] which required about 6 mL of sample, a yellow-green color is shown for the analysis of antidepressants [46] and antidiabetic drugs [55] which used only 1 mL of sample. For this criterion, the highest greenness is assigned to microanalytical methods, with sample sizes of 1–10 mg or μL .

Criterion 3 of the AGREE tool refers to the positioning of the analytical device, with on-line analysis assigned the highest greenness. All of the FPSE-based methods assessed used an off-line system, receiving a red color on the pictograms except for the on-line extraction and analysis of heavy metals [34] which displayed a yellow-green color.

Every FPSE-based method assessed involved 3 or fewer steps, thus had green color for the criterion 4 of the pictogram. For criterion 5, most of the methods were performed manually and were not miniaturized, hence, a red color can be seen on the pictograms. Miniaturization was assigned to the analytical methods for antidepressants [46] and antidiabetic drugs [55] which used only 1 mL of the sample and displayed a yellow color for criterion 5 on their pictograms. Yellow color can also be observed for the analysis of metals [34] since it is semi-automated. The criterion 6 requires the avoidance of derivatization. All of the FPSE-based methods did not require derivatization and received green color on the pictograms except for the analysis of NSAIDs which require derivatization with *N-tert-butyltrimethylsilyl-N-methyltrifluoroacetamide* (MTBSTFA) [32] making it less green for criterion 6.

The amount of waste in criterion 7 of the AGREE tool includes the waste generated during the analysis like the mobile phases in the liquid chromatography techniques. The amount of sample is included in the total waste only when it is in contact with toxic or corrosive substances. There was no FPSE-based method evaluated with waste of more than 100 mL (or g) which would have red color for criterion 7 on its pictogram. Reddish color can be observed for the analysis of 14 PPCPs [38], six UV filters [49], and three parabens [42] which generated about 66 mL, 68 mL, and 63 mL of total waste, respectively. Orange colors can be seen on the pictograms for the methods which generated waste around 10 to 25 mL, while yellow colors for methods with total waste between 0.2 mL and 10 mL. The greenest method for this criterion was the solvent-less extraction and analysis of three PAHs [44] which only produced waste from the FPSE sorbent itself.

In criterion 8, the analytical throughput is assessed which is obtained by multiplying the number of analytes determined per analytical run by the number of samples that can be analyzed in 1 h. Most of the FPSE-based methods evaluated received green colors for criterion 8 on their pictograms (Table 2) since they were analyses of multiple analytes and multiple samples can be analyzed in 1 h. Yellow color can be seen for the analysis of aluminum since it was a single analyte and only 7.5 samples can be analyzed in 1 h [41]. A yellow color can also be seen for the analysis of pesticide residues, as only two analytes can be determined and only 2.4 samples can be analyzed per hour [48].

The criterion 9 of AGREE metric refers to the energy consumption of the analytical method. The most energy consuming equipment used during the extraction and analysis was identified for the methods evaluated. FPSE-based methods which employed mass spectrometry-based analytical techniques received red colors for criterion 9 of their pictograms. Methods which used high performance liquid chromatography received yellow colors, while the analysis of anthracyclines by ultra-performance liquid chromatography [52] received a green color. The analysis of three PAHs by benchtop ion mobility spectrometer also obtained a green color on its pictogram [44].

The use of renewable reagents relates to criterion 10. Since the FPSE-based methods assessed did not explicitly mention the source of their reagents, it was assumed that some of the chemicals were bio-based

(natural fibers, degradable polymers, green solvents), thus most of them received a yellow color for criterion 10 on their pictograms. On the other hand, criterion 11 refers to the amount of toxic reagents used. Methods which used methanol during the extraction or as mobile phase were considered less green according to this criterion since the solvent is toxic if inhaled or ingested. The analysis of six UV filters used around 57.25 mL of methanol (40 mL for FPSE membrane cleaning, 2.25 as eluting solvent, and 15 mL as mobile phase) [49] and received a red color for criterion 11 on its pictogram. No toxic reagents were used for the analysis of four NSAIDs [32], heavy metals [34], three brominated flame retardants [37], eight multiclass emerging contaminants [43], three PAHs [44], four fluoroquinolones [50], and ten phthalates [56], hence they all received green color for criterion 11 on their pictograms. The rest of the methods had yellow to orange colors depending on the amount of toxic reagents used.

Finally, criterion 12 considers the number of hazards associated with the reagents, including those that are toxic to aquatic life, bio-accumulative, persistent, highly flammable, highly oxidizable, explosive or corrosive. The color on the pictogram for criterion 12 changes from green to red according to the increasing number of threats. The FPSE-based methods assessed received either light green or yellow-green colors on their pictograms indicating that the chemicals used were either only highly flammable or both highly flammable and corrosive. The greenest method for this criterion was the analysis of three PAHs [44] which did not use any solvent and thus did not have any threat.

The average overall AGREE score of the FPSE-based methods evaluated was 0.49 indicating a relatively satisfactory level of greenness. The highest total AGREE score was 0.62 which was obtained by the method for the analysis of three PAHs [44] since the analytical throughput was high, energy consumption was very low, no toxic reagents used, very low amount of waste was generated, and there was no chemical threat to the operator and the environment. On the other hand, the lowest total AGREE score of 0.4 was obtained by the method for the analysis of 14 PPCPs [38] because it involved the use of large volume of sample and toxic reagents, generated large amount of waste, and used high energy consuming analytical technique.

3.3. Practicality of FPSE-based methods according to BAGI

BAGI was used to assess the practicality of FPSE-based methods for the analysis of contaminants in water. The methods were evaluated according to ten criteria shown in Table 1. The results of the evaluation are presented in Table 2.

Criterion 1 refers to the type of analysis, where qualitative, screening, quantitative, and quantitative and confirmatory correspond to a white, light blue, blue, and dark blue, respectively on the first segment of the pictogram. Most of the FPSE-based methods evaluated received dark blue for this criterion because they used detectors capable of quantifying and confirming the analytes, while blue color can be seen for the remaining methods.

The second criterion for practicality is the number of analytes. Single analyte analyses like the FPSE-FAAS [34] for lead or cadmium and FPSE-HPLC-UV for aluminum [41] were the least practical among the methods evaluated and received white color on the second segment of their pictograms. Most of the methods were capable of analyzing 2 to 5 analytes or 6 to 15 analytes, which received light blue or blue color, respectively on their pictograms. The most practical methods assessed for this criterion which received dark blue color on their pictograms were the analysis of fungicides [45], pharmaceuticals [47], and pesticides [54] with more than 15 analytes.

The analytical technique used for the analysis concerns criterion 3. The most practical method for this criterion is the one which uses portable instrumentation, hence the analysis of PAHs using benchtop IMS [44] received dark blue color on the third segment of its pictogram. Less practicality was noted for most methods using simple instrumentation like HPLC or FAAS and received blue color on their pictograms

(Table 2). MS-based instrumentation for the analysis of NSAIDs [32], multiclass emerging contaminants [43], and multiclass pesticides [54] received light blue color for criterion 3 of their pictograms. Tandem MS-based methods were the least practical (white color) according to this criterion as this instrumentation is not commonly available in most laboratories.

In criterion 4, the number of samples that can be prepared simultaneously is assessed. Methods allowing the simultaneous preparation of more than 95 samples are considered the most practical for this criterion and are indicated by dark blue color, followed by methods preparing 13 – 95 samples which are indicated by blue. Most of the methods evaluated received blue color on the fourth segment of their pictograms since the FPSE can accommodate up to 20 samples by using two magnetic stirrers with ten samples each. Different FPSE approaches such as stir bar-FPSE [37,50] and dynamic FPSE [38] could only accommodate 2 – 12 samples at a time, and therefore received light blue color on the pictograms. On the other hand, the disk-FPSE for the analysis of metals can accommodate only one sample at a time, and it is therefore the least practical (white color).

The sample preparation technique is assessed in criterion 5, in which FPSE is categorized as miniaturized extraction method. Thus, all the methods assessed received a light blue color (less practical) on the fifth segment of the pictograms. Methods without sample preparation or on-site sample preparation are denoted as the most practical, while methods involving multiple steps are the least practical for this criterion.

Criterion 6 refers to the overall sample throughput considering the sample preparation and the analysis. The most practical methods according to this criterion had sample throughput of more than 10 samples per hour: the analysis of heavy metals [34] (30 samples per hour) and analysis of PAHs [44] (30 samples per hour) which both received dark blue color on the sixth segment of their pictograms. Most of the methods evaluated had acceptable practicality, with sample throughputs of 5 – 10 and 2 – 4 samples per hour which were indicated by blue and light blue color, respectively on their pictograms. The least practical methods according to this criterion were indicated by white color on their pictograms, such as the analysis of PPCPs [30,38], NSAIDs [32], brominated flame retardants [37], pesticide residues [48], UV filters [49], and multiclass pesticides [54] which only had a sample throughput of 1 sample per hour due to longer extraction time and/or longer analysis time.

In criterion 7, the reagents and materials are assessed with practicality increasing according to their availability: requiring synthesis in the laboratory using advanced equipment, requiring synthesis in the laboratory using common instrument, commercially available but not common in the laboratory, and commercially available and common in the laboratory. These correspond to white, light blue, blue, and dark blue colors, respectively on the pictogram. Since the FPSE membranes need to be synthesized using commonly available laboratory equipment, all of the methods assessed had low practicality, indicated by light blue color on the seventh segment of their pictograms.

The method is practical according to criterion 8 of the BAGI tool when no preconcentration is required while achieving the sensitivity and/or legislation requirements. Most of the methods evaluated did not have preconcentration step and were therefore practical, indicated by dark blue color on the eighth segment of their pictograms. The analysis of PPCPs [30,38], triazine herbicides [33], antidepressants [46], pharmaceuticals [47], benzoyl urea insecticides [51], and anthracyclines [52] required preconcentration step, therefore they were less practical methods and received blue color on their pictograms. The analysis of NSAIDs [32] was the least practical with white color indicated on the pictogram due to preconcentration and derivatization steps.

The degree of automation is related to criterion 9. Fully automated analysis is the most practical while manual treatment and analysis is the least practical, indicated by dark blue and white color on the ninth segment of the pictogram. Less practicality is given for semi-automated methods using common or non-common devices corresponding to blue

and light blue color, respectively on the pictogram. Most of the methods evaluated were done manually while some used autosamplers during the analysis, therefore their pictograms received either white or blue color on the ninth segment.

Lastly, criterion 10 relates to the samples amount. The practicality of the method for this criterion decreases with the increasing amount of sample, for instance 10 mL or less, 10.1 – 50 mL, 51 – 100 mL, and greater than 100 mL of sample volume correspond to dark blue, blue, light blue, and white color, respectively on the tenth segment of the pictogram. Most of the FPSE-based methods assessed used less than or equal to 10 mL of sample volume, therefore received dark blue color on their pictograms. The analysis of NSAIDs [32], UV stabilizers [35], PPCPs [38], PAHs [39], fungicides [45], anthracyclines [52], phthalates [56], and EDCs [57] used sample volumes greater than 10 mL but less than 51 mL, and were therefore less practical, indicated by a blue color on their pictograms. The analysis of triazine herbicides [33], benzoyl urea insecticides [51], and multiclass pesticides [54] required 100 mL of sample volume and therefore received a light blue on their pictograms. The least practical method (white color) for this criterion was the analysis of UV filters [49] which required a sample volume of 150 mL.

For each criterion, points were assigned according to decreasing practicality: 10, 7.5, 5, and 2.5 points for dark blue, blue, light blue, and white, respectively. The total scores were obtained by adding the points for each criterion, with a maximum score of 100. The average total BAGI score was 67, which shows that FPSE-based methods can be considered as practical. All of the methods were practical according to the metric tool, with BAGI scores of greater than 60 [21], except for the analysis of NSAIDs [32], PPCPs [38], UV filters [49], and benzoyl urea insecticides [51]. The lowest BAGI score of 55 was obtained by the analytical method for UV filters [49] due to the use of large sample volume, manual treatment and analysis, and low sample throughput. On the other hand, the most practical method, with the highest BAGI score of 75, was the analytical method for antidiabetic drugs [55] as the analysis required minimal sample volume and provided quantitative/confirmatory results without preconcentration.

3.4. Greenness and practicality of FPSE-based methods

Based on the evaluations performed, the FPSE-based methods developed for the analysis of contaminants in environmental water samples can be considered generally green and practical (Fig. 2b), according to the applied metric tools. As shown in Fig. 3, the AGREE scores exhibited a wider range compared to the BAGI scores, suggesting greater variability in greenness among the methods, while practicality remained relatively consistent. Overall, most FPSE-based methods appear to be practical but not necessarily highly green.

To explore whether greener methods also tend to be more practical, a scatter plot of the normalized AGREE and BAGI scores was generated. As shown in Fig. 4b, Method 17 demonstrated both high greenness and practicality, whereas Methods 11 and 22 exhibited the lowest values for both metrics. A Spearman's correlation analysis performed on the normalized scores yielded a rho value of 0.24 (p -value = 0.19), indicating that there is insufficient evidence to support even a weak correlation between greenness and practicality in FPSE-based methods. Additional data would therefore be needed to more conclusively assess whether greener methods are also more practical.

It is also important to recognize potential trade-offs between greenness, practicality, and analytical sensitivity. For instance, although advanced instrumentation such as MS-based techniques may not be considered particularly green, they are often essential for the trace-level analysis of environmental contaminants.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed as an exploratory multivariate tool to assess similarity, grouping, and overall trends among FPSE-based methods based on multiple normalized performance metrics. PCA combines multiple evaluation criteria into a small number of composite variables (principal components) that summarize the main

Fig. 5. PCA biplot of the FPSE-based methods according to their metric scores.

sources of variation among the methods. This allows the identification of natural groupings of methods with similar overall performance, such as those that are both green and practical. In addition, PCA indicates which criteria contribute most to the observed differences between methods through the component loadings, providing an objective, data-driven visualization rather than a subjective ranking of scores. PC1 explained 77.2% of the total variance, while PC2 explained 15.2%, with the remaining variance accounted for by higher components. The PCA biplot (Fig. 5) revealed that the metric tools differentiated the FPSE-based methods into distinct clusters.

Cluster A, consisting of Methods 10a, 10b, 10c, and 23, showed the highest SPMS and AGREEprep scores, indicating that these methods are particularly green as sample preparation techniques. These methods used 10 mL sample for less than 30 min extraction time and generated less than 15 mL of waste (including the sample itself). The biplot also highlighted differences between the SPMS and AGREEprep metrics, reflected in the formation of Clusters B and C. Cluster B (Methods 17 and 5) included methods with high AGREEprep but low SPMS scores, whereas Cluster C (Methods 22 and 11) included methods with high SPMS but low AGREEprep scores. Methods 17 and 5 both did not use toxic organic solvents while Methods 22 and 11 had low energy requirements.

Cluster D (Methods 13, 15, and 3) displayed high BAGI but low AGREE scores, indicating that these methods are practical but less green. Methods 13, 15, and 3 were quantitative and confirmatory for the analysis of multiple analytes though they used high volume of toxic solvents and generated high amount of waste. In contrast, Cluster E (Methods 19, 25, and 6) showed high scores in both AGREE and BAGI, suggesting that these methods are green and practical as complete analytical methods, though not necessarily as sample preparation techniques. These methods were quantitative and confirmatory for the analysis of multiple analytes and used minimal volume of solvents. However, these methods require additional step in the sample preparation (evaporation or reconstitution). Finally, Cluster F, composed of Methods 1, 28, 18, 29, and 30, was located near the origin of the PCA biplot. These methods demonstrated balanced performance, being green both as sample preparation techniques and as complete analytical methods, while also exhibiting satisfactory practicality. The methods had less than 1 h of extraction without additional steps generating minimal amount of waste and quantified multiple analytes using readily

available instrumentation.

4. Conclusion

Due to its many advantages, FPSE has been applied for the analysis of contaminants in environmental water samples. Using metric tools, the greenness and the practicality of FPSE-based methods were quantified, revealing specific areas for improvement. According to these assessments, FPSE is a green and practical technique for the extraction of contaminants from aqueous samples. Its greenness and practicality of FPSE can be further enhanced by reducing the use of toxic solvents for membrane cleaning and conditioning, implementing automation, exploring on-site sample preparation, further miniaturization, increasing sample throughput, and employing less energy-intensive instrumentation. This work provides a robust benchmark for future FPSE developments and provides a clear roadmap for advancing the technique toward even greater environmental and operational sustainability.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Augusto Misolas: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mohamad Sleiman:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Vasilios Sakkas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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